

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.5442 Max: 62.9616	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1199 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic
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In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 673-680	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION yellowish layer below 1177	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1177	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX clay 20% silt 60% sand 20%
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery M <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nails R <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles M <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Amphorae R <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Charcoal R <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones R <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth R <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1177	Covers: 1203
Is cut by:	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS Brown which dries to yellowish color. Not super-compact or clay-ish. Excavated with pickaxe and shovel, using trowels to define next layer (1203) or bedrock. Day was humid (for Caabi) and sunny. Finished excavating in 1 workday. Special Find 190 found in middle of this SU.

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: Southwestern corner (bounded by wall on W side, floor prep and bedrock on E side, floor on N side, and bulk on S side)
Shape: Rounded Rectangular

For layers complete this section:
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): No slope
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) No clusters of inclusions, everything deposited throughout layer
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): 15-ish cm thick, pretty even, no changes in thickness, even by hole feature
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

For cuts complete this section:
Cut edges: rounded straight
Cut sides: straight concave convex sloping
Cut bottom: flat concave irregular
How is cut top edge? sharp rounded
How is cut bottom edge? sharp rounded
Observations:

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

This SU fills what could be a cut into the bedrock (which is covered by 1173). Defined from 1177 because of its darker color and higher compaction and differs from 1203 because 1203 is darker (more black than brown) and slightly more granular.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets): _____

Sample quantity (buckets): 2

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CKazemis & A Bryck	on	20-7-2010
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